

Jakarta, Banten and Extension of the Implementation of Large Scale Social Restrictions Management during Covid-19

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Reading the news about the spread of Covid 19, or often called Corona, makes us have to frown. How not, until the middle of May 2020, there are no signs that the Corona Virus will end up being overcome by the Government. The government has so far not been able to ensure that the Corona emergency will end. Based on data released by the Indonesian Ministry of Health as of May 12, 2020, there is very alarming information, where 14,749 people have tested positive for Co-19, and died as many as 1,007. The number of ODP (people under surveillance) was 251,861, the number of PDP was 32. 147. And the number of patients declared cured was 3,063

Various attempts have been made by the government, both the central and regional governments. From the start of lockdown, quarantine of the region until the PSBB has been carried out. But what happened was not a reduction, but an increasing number of people tested positive for Covid-19. We already know that several regional heads, with their authority, have established various policies to anticipate the spread of Covid-19 in their respective regions. Starting from the Governor of DKI, Governor of West Java, and not behind the Governor of Banten also participated in issuing strategic policies to anticipate the spread of Covid-19.

Jakarta Governor Anies Baswedan, for example, long before the central government issued a regulation on the adoption of the PSBB, the Governor of DKI had asked the central government for the DKI to apply a lockdown. Not only that on April 30, 2020 the Governor of DKI Jakarta has also issued Regulation Number 41 of 2020 concerning Imposition of Sanctions Against Violations of the Implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions in Handling Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) in the Special Capital Region Province of Jakarta. And on March 18, 2020, Governor Instruction Number 23 of 2020 has also been issued on Optimizing the anticipation and prevention of transmission of coronavirus disease (covid-19) by maintaining a safe distance between citizens in the community (social distancing measure) in the community aimed at the Mayor intended to the Mayor DKI, sub-district heads, urban village heads throughout Jakarta.

In the instruction, the Mayor and Regent of the Jakarta Provincial Administration, were asked to Encourage the Sub-District Heads and Lurahs to do a mapping of citizens who were or after traveling from Abroad and the potential to cause and spread Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19); The instruction also asked the relevant authorities to coordinate with the Task Force for the Acceleration of Coronavirus Disease Handling (COVID-19) of DKI Jakarta Province; and also invites the City Council to be able to help socialize the optimization of anticipating the prevention and transmission of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) by maintaining a safe distance between citizens in the community (Social Distancing Measure) in the Community Environment.

To the Subdistricts and Lurahs, the Governor of DKI Jakarta invites all the Neighborhood Associations, Community Associations, Family Consultation Institutions, Empowerment and Family Welfare, Youth Organization and other Community Institutions and community leaders to be able to help socialize the optimization of anticipating the prevention and transmission of Coronavirus Disease (COVID- 19) by maintaining a safe distance between citizens in the community (Social Distancing Measure) in the Community Environment by; not allowed to leave the house except for important activities and its nature can not be postponed, wherever possible to conduct long-distance meetings; avoid potential places where transmission can occur, such as areas full of visitors, and places to stand and / or sit close together; The Governor also postponed all activities related to gathering citizens / masses, even if the activities were good, important and noble but if not very important and urgent (Urgent), for example social gathering, recitation, meetings, majelis ta'lim and so on, please postpone first , until the condition of transmission of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) can be controlled;

Furthermore, in the governor's instruction, the DKI Provincial Government urges the public not to leave the house except for important activities which cannot be postponed; instructing the public to always maintain personal hygiene by: washing hands with soap regularly and frequently; avoid shaking hands or kissing on the cheeks and use other methods to greet each other without having to touch; wear a mask if you have a cold and / or cough and make sure.

Relating to religious activities and worship as much as possible in their respective homes and delaying all activities that are carried out together until the condition of transmission of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) can be controlled properly. And also the public is asked to postpone the reception activities, if the wedding reception activities must be carried out, the organizers must take firm and disciplined steps including, a) there must be an attendant's body temperature checker before entering the event room; b). provide isolation space for guests if found to be unhealthy. c) Provide Hand Sanitizers at the entrances and exits; and d) are not allowed to shake hands / shake hands and interact without touching;

Another point in Instructions number 23 of 2020 issued by the DKI Jakarta Provincial Government is to urge residents not to travel outside the City, postpone plans for going home until Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) transmission is well controlled, the aim is to avoid transmission and spread of Coronavirus Disease. (COVID-19); and no less important is reminding Parents to supervise their children not to travel, because the risk of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) transmission is currently high, the elimination of

learning activities in schools, the abolition of learning activities on Campus / University should not be considered as a holiday period, but aims to all be in their respective homes

What about Banten province?

In an online media release released on March 15, 2020, Banten Governor Wahidin Halim set the status of an extraordinary event (KLB) for the corona virus outbreak in Banten Province. The status determination is stated in SK Number: 443 / Kep.114-Huk / 2020. This determination follows the existence of four Banten residents who tested positive for corona virus (Covid-19). The establishment of the Covid-19 KLB is one of the efforts of the Provincial Government (Pemprov) of Banten to prevent and localize the velocity / exposure of the corona virus. The decision to establish the corona virus outbreak was made at a meeting attended by a number of officials in Banten including the Banten Regional Secretary (Sekda) Al Muktabar and at the head of the relevant department or agency within the Banten Provincial Government. In a preparedness meeting to deal with the corona virus which was held on Saturday (3/14/2020), Banten Governor Wahidin Halim gave special instructions to the Education and Culture Office (Dindikbud) of Banten Province. Dindikbud is instructed to dismiss high school / vocational / SKh students both public and private to conduct learning activities at home for two weeks (14 days) from 16-30 March 2020

Banten Governor Wahidin Halim officially issued a Governor Regulation (Pergub) on the Large-Scale Social Restriction (PSBB) for the Greater Tangerang area. The policy to accelerate the handling of corona virus or COVID-19 starts on Saturday (18/4) to Sunday (3/5). The regulation was issued after a decision by the central government to improve the status of the Greater Tangerang region was included in the red zone of the spread of the corona virus and PSBB was implemented in conjunction with DKI Jakarta. Tangerang Raya covers Tangerang Regency, Tangerang City and South Tangerang City.

In the Governor's Regulation on PSBB number 16 of 2020 it regulates the activities of residents outside their homes who live in the Greater Tangerang area. Activities outside the home in question are such as the implementation of learning at school, activities at work in the workplace, religious activities in houses of worship, activities in public places, socio-cultural activities and the movement of people and goods using modes of transportation.

Meanwhile in the implementation of PSBB in the workplace, the Governor did not stop the total factory or office activity. In this regulation, every factory or office in the PSBB period will continue to carry out its activities and implement the protocol that has been set.

If there is one employee who is tested positive for COVID-19, the factory or office is obliged to suspend its activities and require the factory / office to carry out rapid tests independently of all its employees, and for administrative staff to be able to do their work from home.

Covid's budget escort 19

To prevent misuse of the Covid-19 handling budget in Banten Province, Banten Governor Wahidin Halim (WH) expects the help of the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) especially the Korsupgah Task Force to be able to oversee disaster management so that it runs according to the rules and is free from corruption. This was conveyed by the WH Governor when attending the Provincial 2020 Integrated Corruption Eradication Coordination Meeting with the KPK via teleconference on Tuesday (5/5/2020) at the Governor's Official House, Serang City.

In his statement, the WH Governor said that at the moment we are dealing with an abnormal situation, there is a global pandemic namely Covid-19. Our budget refocusing is done to meet the handling of Covid-19 not only from the health aspect, but also from the economic aspects and the needs of the community's life. For that, all must be called and responsible. We involved the BPKP and the Prosecutors' Office, and we also hope that the KPK can take part in overseeing and conducting coaching so that we do not misstep in the use of funds for Covid-19. With a budget for handling Covid-19 is quite large both from the state budget and regional budget.

The WH Governor further stated that the Covid 19 budget must be used in accordance with statutory regulations and on target. The assistance from the KPK, especially from the Korsupgah Task Force to be able to oversee the use of the Covid-19 handling budget, is expected to meet the expectations of the community which is the goal or the focus of the government. The Governor revealed, this was done because the Banten Provincial Government has a strong commitment to preventing corruption. Based on the evaluation results of the implementation of integrated corruption prevention in Banten Province from 2019 to 31 December 2019 covering 8 intervention areas, namely: APBD planning and budgeting, procurement of goods and services, one-stop integrated services, APIP capabilities, ASN management, optimization of regional income and governance village fund, progress based on the results of the Korsupgah KPK team's verification has reached 93, or ranks third nationally from 34 Provinces in Indonesia.

Banten and PSBB Dynamics

Seeing the development of the Covid-19 pandemic in the Greater Tangerang region of Tangerang City, Tangerang Regency and South Tangerang City (Tangsel) and paying attention to the evaluation results of the implementation of the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in the region, Banten Governor Wahidin Halim finally extended the PSBB period from 4 May 2020 to May 17 2020. The decree was stated in the Decree of the Governor (Kepgub) of Banten Number 443 / Kep.149-Huk / 2020 concerning the Determination of the Extension of Large Scale Social Restrictions in Tangerang Regency, Tangerang City, and South Tangerang City in the Context of Accelerating Handling of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID- 19) dated May 2, 2020.

The Governor of Banten explained that observing the Decree of the Minister of Health No. HK.01.07 / MENKES / 249/2020 concerning the Determination of Large-Scale Social Restrictions in the District of Tangerang, Tangerang City, and South Tangerang City, Banten Province has also made Banten Governor Decree Number 443 / Kep. 114-Huk / 2020 concerning Determination of Corona Extraordinary Events (Covid-19) in the Banten Province Area; Decree of the Governor of Banten No. 443 / Kep.140-Huk / 2020

concerning the Establishment of Large-Scale Social Restrictions in the Districts of Tangerang, Tangerang City, and South Tangerang City in the Context of Accelerating the Handling of Corona Virus Disease 2019; Letter of introduction Head of Banten Provincial Health Office Number 800/1348 / Kes-Yan / 2020 dated 29 April 2020 regarding the Request for Consultation on the Decree of the Governor of Banten concerning the Extension of the Implementation of Large Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in handling corona virus disease 2019 (covid-19) in Tangerang Regency, Tangerang City and South Tangerang City regions, the Banten Provincial Government stipulates the extension of PSBB in the Greater Tangerang area in the framework of the Acceleration of COVID-19 Handling in Banten Province.

PSBB extension is carried out for 14 (fourteen) days from 4 May 2020 until 17 May 2020, and can be extended if there is still evidence of the spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). And requesting the Regional Government both Tangerang Regency, Tangerang City and South Tangerang City must implement the PSBB in accordance with the provisions of the Legislation and consistently encourage and promote a clean and healthy lifestyle to the community.

As for the derivative of the Governor Regulation, the time for determining the extension of the PSBB is determined by the Regent / Mayor. Based on the results of previous PSBB evaluations, there is a declining trend in the number of new cases compared to before the implementation of the PSBB. Each region has the right policy in the implementation of the check point because it is adapted to the existing conditions and situations.

Closing

Seeing and witnessing the development of the spread of Covid 19 in Banten Province as of May 15, 2020, we can draw a conclusion that the Government of Banten Province seems slow and unresponsive in handling the spread of the Covid 19 virus. This delay can be seen from the governor's instructions and instructions or letters governor's circular which was published after many people were affected by Corona Virus 19. For example, Banten Governor Decree No. 443 / Kep.114-Huk / 2020 concerning Determination of Corona Extraordinary Events (COVID-19) in Banten Province which was just published on March 14, 2020 And this is very much different from the attitude and response of the Governor of DKI Jakarta, who quickly issued a variety of strategic policies regarding the prevention of Corona Virus 19. One of the responsive forms of DKI Regional Government is the issuance of Number 16 Year 2020 Regarding Increased Awareness of the Risk of Corona Infection Transmission. Virus Disease (Covid-19), published n on February 25, 2020. According to sources in the source on the Website of the Jakarta Information and Documentation Management Officer (PPID), no less than 35 strategic policies issued by the DKI Regional Government in anticipating the spread of Covid 19.

And it is proven, positive appreciation was given by President Joko Widodo regarding PSBB Management which was implemented by the DKI Regional Government. Besides DKI, the President also gave appreciation to Central Java and East Java. And in the end, DKI has become a reference and reference for other provinces in Indonesia in terms of PSBB Management, including Banten. [*]